

MAIN FACTORS OF THE DEGRADATION OF QAMASHI DISTRICT PASTURES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17182410>

Abstract. This article describes the results of geobotanical research carried out in Qamashi district of Kashkadarya region. The main focus is on the area of natural pastures and hayfields in the district, the excessive, continuous, and unregulated grazing of livestock on pasturelands, as well as a comparative analysis with the results of previous studies conducted in past years.

Keywords: geobotanical research, pasture and hayfield, pasture types, pasture productivity, degradation, cultural-technical condition of pastures.

Introduction

In recent years, under conditions of climate change, the growing population in our country has led to an increase in demand for agricultural products. In meeting the population's need for agricultural goods through the development of livestock farming particularly in supplying ecologically clean meat products- the natural pastures and hayfields of our republic serve as an important natural resource.

Unfortunately, in recent years, a decline in productivity at varying levels, as well as an increase in degraded pasturelands, has been observed across much of these pastures and hayfields. For this reason, it has become one of the most urgent issues of today to conduct scientific research aimed at studying the state of pasture vegetation in these areas, the share of degraded lands, the degree of vegetation cover, the level of water supply to pastures (wells and other sources), the negative effects of overgrazing, the duration and norms of grazing, developing improved standards based on global experience, establishing strict management, preserving the diminishing forage and medicinal pasture plants by supporting their seed reproduction, and developing strategic management measures that increase the efficiency of sustainable use.

It should be noted that, in order to ensure the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Pastures” adopted on May 20, 2019 [1]; the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan N. PD–277 of June 10, 2022 “On Measures to Create an Effective System for Combating Land Degradation”; as well as the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of April 23, 2018 No. 299 “On Measures to Further Improve the Procedure for Carrying Out Geobotanical Research on Pastures and Hayfields, Demarcating Administrative-Territorial Boundaries, and Inventorying Land Resources” [2], work is being carried out across the republic to inventory pastures and hayfields and to conduct geobotanical research [3].

In recent years, it has been established that in the mountain, foothill, and desert pastures of our country, degradation processes have intensified over the past 40 years. The diversity and productivity of pasture vegetation have declined, and the area per one conditional livestock unit has increased by an average of 6.1 hectares. According to geobotanical assessments, the studied mountain and foothill pastures were rated as “medium,” while desert pastures were rated as “low” [M. Ruzmetov, 2021, p. 69].

Research object and methods.

The object of the research is the pasture vegetation of Qamashi district in Kashkadarya region. Geobotanical studies were carried out using methods widely applied in this field [6, 7, 9]. Based on the degree of vegetation cover in mountain and foothill pasture areas, electronic digital maps at a scale of 1:25,000 were created using the ArcGIS program.

Research results and discussion.

The studies revealed the present characteristics and condition of the existing pastures. In addition, within the framework of combating land degradation processes, the following tasks are being implemented:

- developing and conducting a unified state policy in the field of combating land degradation;
- preparing state programs and forward-looking strategies to fight land degradation processes, and coordinating the activities of ministries and agencies involved in their implementation;
- collecting, analyzing, processing, and providing open access to information within a unified electronic resource (database) about land degradation, desertification, drought, and measures taken against them;
- applying modern technologies (laboratories, drones, remote sensing, etc.) in line with national and international indicators and criteria to monitor land degradation and desertification, including land restoration, reclamation, and amelioration activities; rotational use of pastures, their conservation and phytomelioration; crop rotation; and afforestation and shelterbelt creation.

Based on the distribution of forage plants in the district, their growing conditions, and floristic composition, the pastures were classified into 3 pasture groups, 5 pasture types, and 12 pasture varieties.

In the pastures located near residential areas and livestock enclosures, overgrazing throughout all seasons of the year has caused the plant cover to become somewhat sparse. Due to livestock consuming plants before they reach their reproductive phase as a result of excessive grazing, this situation has had a serious negative impact on the continuity of plant generations. Within the district, there are a total of 92,487.5 hectares of pastureland, of which 9,673.7 hectares, or 10.5%, have been found to be degraded to varying degrees under the influence of humans and livestock.

Soil, agrochemical, and geobotanical studies, land surveys, aerial and satellite imaging, topographic-geodetic, and cartographic work are being carried out to preserve pasture productivity. Scientifically grounded recommendations are being developed to prevent land degradation processes. In addition, cartographic materials are being created based on soil salinity and ecological condition (Soil Quality Index), as well as geobotanical and agrochemical maps.

For enterprises, institutions, organizations, and other responsible officials in charge of combating land degradation, mandatory instructions have been issued on preventing land degradation and eliminating its negative consequences. According to geobotanical research conducted in 1983, the dry mass yield of the district's forage pasture plants was 4.4 centners per hectare, and the feed unit was 2.6 centners per hectare. In 2024, the yield of pasture plants decreased to an average of 3.7 centners per hectare (-0.7 c/ha), while the feed unit decreased to 2.0 centners per hectare (-0.6 c/ha).

Research also recorded a decline in the share of forage plant species due to an increase in non-forage species across the district. In other words, the proportion of plants not consumed by

livestock increased from 10–13% to 17–22% (on average 23%). The cultural-technical condition of the land, from lower to higher levels, transitions into rodent burrows, stony areas, rocky outcrops, and shrub thickets. Specifically, rodent burrows cover 1–3%, eroded areas up to 1–5%, stony areas up to 2–7%, shrub thickets up to 1–9%, exposed bedrock up to 1–5%, and rocky outcrops up to 1–7%.

Based on the obtained data, it was proposed to use modern unmanned aerial vehicles to sow the seeds of plants such as sagebrush, wormwood and annual saltworts, which are less common forage plants for livestock, onto degraded lands during the rainy seasons. This measure aims to enrich pasture vegetation in these areas and replace less-consumed grasses in meadows with more valuable forage plants. These recommendations were submitted to the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as to regional and district local government authorities.

Conclusion

As noted above, based on the conducted studies, proposals and recommendations were also developed for the studied areas to prepare a plan for the effective, integrated use of pastures for the population. This includes organizing rotational grazing of livestock across pasturelands and establishing enclosed areas for controlled grazing. [4]

Proposals and Recommendations for Pasture Restoration:

- Rehabilitating pastures by supporting the natural processes that maintain soil fertility and the quantitative and qualitative condition of plant cover, as well as establishing seed production plantations in cooperation with pasture management associations.
- Developing new water sources in pasture areas, including wells, water pipelines, livestock watering points, and passage systems.
- Establishing protective shelterbelts of trees and shrubs in desert areas to combat soil and wind erosion in degraded lands.

- Using modern unmanned aerial vehicles (drones) to sow seeds of forage plants that are currently scarce such as sagebrush, wormwood and annual saltworts onto degraded lands during rainy seasons. This will help enrich pasture vegetation and replace less-consumed grasses in meadows with more valuable forage plants.

As a result of implementing these measures in a comprehensive manner, the number of valuable forage plant species in intensively used pastures will increase, ultimately raising pasture plant productivity to 8-10 centners per hectare.

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